

EFFECTS OF INTERFACIAL TREATMENT USING L-LACTIC ACID ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF β -TCP/PLLA COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Bioabsorbable Materials, Poly(L-Lactic acid), β -Tricalcium Phosphate, Interfacial Treatment*

1 Introduction

In order to avoid secondary surgery of removing metallic implants imposed on patients with bone defects, poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA), poly(glycolic acid), poly ϵ -caprolactone, and their copolymers have attracted wide attentions for their biodegradability in the human body. However, mechanical properties of those materials were lower than that of natural cortical bones. Thus, in order to improve mechanical properties, biocompatibility, and osteoconductivity, combinations of polymers with bioactive ceramics such as hydroxyapatite (HA) and β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) have been investigated [1-5]. Actually, stiffness of such kinds of composites is improved, whereas strength becomes lower because of the lower interfacial strength between the bioceramics particles and polymer matrix. For this reason, various methods, such as surface modification of HA particles with silane [6-8], polyethylene glycol [9], isocyanate [10, 11], poly acids [12-14] and dodecyl alcohol [15], have been developed to improve adhesion between bioceramics and polymeric matrix. In these cases, mechanical properties were improved to some extent, but most of these were toxic to humans. Hong et al. reported that a L-lactide grafted HA/PLLA composite showed higher tensile strength than non-treated HA/PLLA [16]. Also Kunze et al. studied activation of TCP surface with phosphoric acid and activated HA was modified by L-lactide and ϵ -caprolactone. Although NMR spectrum indicated a covalent attachment of lactic acid units onto the phosphorus, mechanical properties of modified TCP/poly(D,L-lactide) were not improved [17].

In this study, β -TCP was used as bioabsorbable ceramic filler. We prepared β -TCP/PLLA composites by kneading interfacially-treated β -TCP particles with L-lactic acid and PLLA and hot-

pressing. In order to investigate effects of interfacial treatments on the mechanical properties, tensile tests were conducted on the β -TCP/PLLA composites.

2 Methods

2.1 Materials

As a reinforcement, β -TCP particles (Rasa Koei Co., Tokyo, Japan) was used. A matrix material used was PLLA (Lacty#5000, Shimadzu Co., Kyoto, Japan). L-lactic acid (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd, Osaka, Japan) was used as an interfacial treatment agent.

2.2 Interfacial Treatment

In order to improve interfacial strength between PLLA and β -TCP, β -TCP surface was treated with L-lactic acid solution.

First, 12 g L-lactic acid was added to 300 ml purified water. Then, 200 g β -TCP was dispersed to L-lactic acid solution. The suspension was stirred with a stirrer for 3 hours and evaporated in a hot water bath for 3 hours. These were followed by drying in an oven at 80 °C. After water was removed completely, β -TCP treated with 12g L-lactic acid was sieved.

Furthermore, in order to examine the effect of amount of L-lactic acid on mechanical properties of the composites, the amount of L-lactic acid was changed to 6, 9, 15 or 24 g.

β -TCP treated with 6, 9, 12, 15 and 24 g was labeled as β -TCP-3, 4.5, 6, 7.5 and 12 phr (=amount/100).

2.3 Thermal Gravimetric Analysis

Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to determine the amount of L-lactic acid on β -TCP surface. The measurements were conducted from room temperature to 700 °C, at a rate of 5 °C/min under air atmosphere. Measurements were conducted on non-treated and interfacially-treated β -TCP particles.

The amount of L-lactic acid on β -TCP surface was calculated as a difference between weight loss of non-treated β -TCP and that of interfacially-treated β -TCP. Assuming that L-lactic acid uniformly coated β -TCP surface, the nominal ratio of interphase thickness to β -TCP grain size (t/r) was calculated according to the following equation (1),

$$\frac{t}{r} = \frac{1}{3} \frac{\rho_{\beta\text{-TCP}}}{\rho_{\text{L-lactic acid}}} \frac{W_{\text{L-lactic acid}}}{W_{\beta\text{-TCP}}} \quad (1)$$

where t is interphase thickness, r is β -TCP grain size. $\rho_{\beta\text{-TCP}}$ and $\rho_{\text{L-lactic acid}}$ are densities of β -TCP and L-lactic acid, respectively. $W_{\beta\text{-TCP}}$ and $W_{\text{L-lactic acid}}$ are weights of β -TCP and L-lactic acid, respectively.

2.4 Preparation of β -TCP/PLLA Composites

Non-treated and interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA compounds were obtained by kneading. β -TCP/PLLA composites with β -TCP content of 15 wt% and 30 wt% were prepared. PLLA and β -TCP were kneaded at 200 °C and at 50 rpm for 20 min with a batch-type mixer (IMC-1882, Imoto Co.).

Compounds obtained were crushed into small pieces with a mill (SM-1, HSIANGTAI). Then the crushed compounds were used to make composite plates by hot-pressing. The compounds were remelted at 200 °C for 20 min, and then pressed for 5 min. After cooling to 30 °C, a composite plate (170 mm \times 170 mm \times 3 mm) was obtained and cut into specimens of 100 mm \times 10 mm \times 3 mm in shape for tensile tests.

2.5 Tensile Testing

Before tensile test, Aluminum tabs were glued on both ends of specimens for preventing stress concentration. Strain gauges were also glued on center of specimens.

Tensile tests were carried out using a universal testing machine (AGS-1000A, Shimadzu) at room temperature. The crosshead speed was 1 mm/min.

The tensile strength and modulus were calculated from the stress-strain relationship.

2.6 Scanning electron microscopy

After tensile test, fracture surfaces of samples were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). All surface were coated with a thin layer of platinum prior of SEM examination.

2.7 Differential Scanning Calorimetry

For investigating crystallinity of β -TCP/PLLA composites, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were conducted at heating rate 5 °C/min from room temperature to 220 °C.

Crystallinity of PLLA (X_c) in composite was calculated from the following formula,

$$\chi_c = \frac{\Delta H_{m,composite}}{\Delta H_{PLLA,100\%}} \times \frac{M_c}{M_m} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta H_{m,composite}$ was melting enthalpy (J/g), $\Delta H_{PLLA,100\%}$ was theoretical enthalpy of completely crystalline PLLA (135 J/g [18]). M_c and M_m were weight of composites and PLLA matrix in β -TCP/PLLA, respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 TGA

Figure 1 shows the weight losses of β -TCP particles. The weight loss of non-treated β -TCP was 3.1 %, while weight losses of interfacially-treated β -TCP-3, 4.5, 6, 7.5, and 12 phr were 4.8 %, 5.4 %, 6.4 %, 7.2 % and 9.1 %, respectively. The amount of L-lactic acid on surface of β -TCP was determined as difference between weight losses of non-treated and interfacially-treated β -TCP. Thus the amount of L-lactic acid on surfaces of β -TCP-3, 4.5, 6, 7.5 and 12 phr were 1.7 %, 2.3 %, 3.3 %, 4.1 % and 6.0 %, respectively. The amount of L-lactic acid on β -TCP surface increased with L-lactic acid used for interfacial treatment.

Relationship between t/r and the amount of L-lactic acid was calculated according to eq. (1) and shown in Fig. 2. t/r increased approximately linearly with increasing amount of L-lactic acid.

Adhesion strength between PLLA matrix and β -TCP is considered to be improved by introduction of interphase. However, excessive interphase thickness causes lower stress transfer to the fillers in the composites, which results in the lower macroscopic properties. Therefore optimization of the interphase thickness would be necessary.

Fig. 1 TGA curves of non-treated β -TCP (a) and β -TCP treated with L-lactic acid 3 phr (b), 4.5 phr (c), 6 phr (d) 7.5 phr (e) and 12 phr (f).

Fig. 2 Relationship between t/r and the amount of L-lactic acid.

3.2 Mechanical Properties

Figure 3 shows tensile strength of non-treated and interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA composites with 15 and 30 wt% β -TCP contents. For all composites, tensile strength decreased with increasing content of β -TCP. Tensile strength of β -TCP-3 phr/PLLA is almost the same as that of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA. As increasing the amount of L-lactic acid from 4.5 to 6 phr, tensile strength increased. At both β -TCP contain of 15 wt% and 30 wt%, β -TCP-6 phr/PLLA exhibited maximum tensile strength. It may seem that interfacial treatment using 6 g L-lactic acid for 100 g β -TCP was optimal for improving interfacial

strength. On the other hand, tensile strength of β -TCP-12 phr/PLLA was much lower than that of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA. This is assumed that stress transfer to the filler was prevented by excessive interphase thickness.

Figure 4 shows tensile modulus of non-treated and interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA. Tensile modulus increased with increasing filler content from 15 wt% to 30 wt%. However little differences between elastic moduli of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA and interfacially-treated β -TCP were observed. Elastic moduli of each interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA were also similar, when the amount of L-lactic acid used was changed from 3 to 12 phr. Therefore, it was found that there is no effect of interfacial treatment and the amount of L-lactic acid on the elastic modulus.

Fig. 3 Tensile strength of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA and interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA.

Fig. 4 Elastic modulus of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA and interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA.

3.3 SEM Observations of Fracture Surfaces

The fracture surfaces of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA and interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA composites after tensile testing were observed by SEM (Fig. 5-10). Unlike fracture surfaces of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA, interfacial debondings appear in part of fracture surfaces of interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA as shown in Fig. 6 (b). Fracture surfaces of interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA composites consist of regions with interfacial debonding and regions with no debonding. The smallest areas of interfacial debonding were observed on surfaces of β -TCP-6 phr/PLLA at both β -TCP contents of 15 wt% and 30 wt%. It was attributed to improved interface adhesion. And enhanced adhesion between PLLA and interfacially-treated β -TCP caused the higher tensile strength of β -TCP-6 phr/PLLA composites.

(a) 15 wt%

(b) 30 wt%

Fig. 5 Fracture surfaces of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA.

(a) 15 wt%

(b) Interfacial debonding (15 wt%)

(c) 30 wt%

Fig. 6 Fracture surfaces of β -TCP-3 phr/PLLA.

(a) 15 wt%

(b) 30 wt%

Fig. 7 Fracture surfaces of β -TCP-4.5 phr/PLLA.

(a) 15 wt%

(b) 30 wt%

Fig. 8 Fracture surfaces of β -TCP-6 phr/PLLA.

(a) 15wt%

(b) 30 wt%

Fig. 9 Fracture surfaces of β -TCP-7.5 phr/PLLA.

(a) 15 wt%

(b) 30 wt%

Fig. 10 Fracture surfaces of β -TCP-12 phr/PLLA.

3.4 DSC

Crystallinities of PLLA matrix were determined by DSC, showing in Fig. 11. Crystallinities of PLLA in the composites slightly increased with increasing β -TCP content from 15 wt% to 30 wt%. It may be attributed to high heat capacity of β -TCP. However among same β -TCP content (15 wt% or 30 wt%), crystallinities of interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA were comparable to non-treated β -TCP/PLLA. Thus it could be thought that the improved mechanical properties of interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA were not attributed to crystallization of PLLA in the composites.

Fig. 11 Crystallinity of PLLA in non-treated β -TCP/PLLA and interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA.

4 Conclusions

In the present study, in order to improve interfacial strength between PLLA and β -TCP, β -TCP surface was treated with 3, 4.5, 6, 7.5 and 12 phr of L-lactic acid solution. The amount of L-lactic acid on β -TCP surface was determined by TGA. Ratio of interphase thickness to β -TCP particle size increased linearly with increasing the amount of L-lactic acid. β -TCP/PLLA compound was obtained by kneading and fabricated into a plate by hot-pressing. Compared with non-treated β -TCP/PLLA composites, both β -TCP contents (15wt% and 30 wt%), β -TCP-12 phr/PLLA exhibits higher tensile strength. On the other hand, interfacial treatments did not affect tensile modulus. SEM observation showed improved interfacial adhesion between β -TCP-6 phr and PLLA. Crystallinity of PLLA in composites was determined by DSC. Crystallinities increased with increasing β -TCP content. However

crystallinities of interfacially-treated β -TCP/PLLA were same as that of non-treated β -TCP/PLLA.

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